

Study on the Diversity of Products Obtained from Sheep in the Current Bioeconomy Context

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Abstract

A concern for the growth and utilization of sheep is raised since ancient times in Romania. The development of livestock sector is determined by the climate and the geographical configuration with the availability of grasslands maintained by transhumants. The pastoralism founded a domestic processing of milk, wool and leather products with positive socio-economic implications on material and spiritual life of local people. The sheep breeds prevailed until the 20th century were 'Tucana' and 'Stogose' and, to a lesser extent, 'Tisigai'. These breeds, generally unimproved, have a profound fitness and resistance to harsh weather conditions. These breeds were also fit for traveling long routes in search of food. The utilization of a sheep breed is determined by the national economic demand, productivity potential of the breed, available, technology, improvement and utilization methods of the breed. The said sheep breeds were appreciated because they produce a diversity of products having superior nutritional or economic values. It is known especially for its white wool, which is used in domestic industry for making clothes and other products including artifacts, textiles, Persian carpets, etc. Considering the local natural conditions and the national economic demands, the sheep husbandry was assisted continuously to support intensive and multilateral development producing the necessary raw materials for the textile, fur, leather and food industry. Both research and the technical developments have contributed to the zootechnical field geared to resolve the problems appeared in the development of sheep. The scientific knowledge and expertise need to be combined with application skills leading to the development and modernization of complex technologies helping growth of sheep products.

Keywords

Sheep; Wool; Milk; Bioeconomy; Meat

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1. Introduction

The sheep (*Ovis vignei*) is appreciated for both the diversity of its products and its superior nutritional and economic values (Alexandru, 2009). Considering the local natural conditions and the demands of the national economy, currently the sheep

breeding is an important sector of animal husbandry, which has been oriented, stimulated and supported to achieve intensive and multilateral development ensuring domestic production of raw materials for the textile, fur, leather and food industries (Alexandru, 2010). This explains why sheep had a spread to the entire globe, more in temperate areas and less in humid cold or humid hot areas. Therefore, sheep products need to be understood through the prism of economic efficiency using recent scientific literature focusing new technologies to harness the productive potential of the sheep (Ilisiu *et al.*, 2013).

Historically, special attention was paid to the practical ways of intensifying the sheep breeding and harnessing the products in the wake of new agriculture revolution in Romania. Interests in sheep increased with the development of agriculture and socio-economic aspects generating new demands for food and raw materials of animal origin (Amalia and Simona, 2019). Thus, the need arose to create new productive breeds of sheep, simultaneously with the recent advancement of breeding and exploration technologies having increased efficiency.

The research and the technical developments have contributed to rising sector of animal husbandry in order to solve the contemporary problems posing sheep breeding. Depending on the evolution of socio-economic factors and the organizational framework, the utilization of sheep evolved through many stages (Gavojdian *et al.*, 2012). However, current trends in sheep farming are based mainly on market requirements, biological characteristics of sheep breeds, and the environmental conditions (see Table 1).

Table 1: The evolution of sheep worldwide 2017-2019

<i>Continent</i>	<i>Number in 2017</i>	<i>Number in 2018</i>	<i>% Change to total in 2019</i>
Africa	164.859	183.562	+1.34
North America	22.410	21.961	-2.92
Asia	293.778	324.561	+21.45
South America	102.563	107.790	6.45
Europe	126.343	134.249	+5.55
Total	1,044.316	1,120.092	+4.15

As highlighted in table 1, large increases in sheep numbers have been recorded in Asia, followed by Africa and Europe, while the other continents mark a slight decrease. In some transoceanic countries, such as Australia and New Zealand, there are large sheep farmers. Until recently the production of sheep is chiefly for harnessing the wool; and now a crossbreed ‘Corriedale’ is raised for meat and wool. In Eastern Europe and the Balkans, the meat production has increased along with wool, milk and skins. A preferred breed of sheep is the one that has medium size, high adaptability and crossbreeding traits with other breeds, and gives mixed production, precociousness and prolificacy. With this background, in the present paper, the Indigenous sheep breeds, Tisigai and Turcana, are analyzed to understand sheep raising practices and to identify the factors that lead to an increase and improvement of wool, milk, and meat production.

2. Study Area

This study concentrates on the growth of the sheep from Prahova area situated in the Carpathian curvature. The breeding area of the two sheep breeds - Tisigai and Turcana - starts from the north of Dambovită area, adjacent to Buzău. This site stretches over an area of 30-40 km on the hilly altitude of 600-800 m.

3. Description of Sheep Breeds

The Țisigai breed (Figure 1) comes from the *Ovis vignei arkal*. From the southeast of the Caspian Sea, where it was domesticated, it spread first into Asia Minor, then in the south of the Soviet Union, and in the Danube Mouth region and Dobrogea (Romania). From here, it spread to the rest of Romania, and to Bulgaria, Yugoslavia, Hungary, Czecho-Slovakia and Poland. Over time, because of transhumance and the geo-climatic conditions in Romania, two ecotypes within Țisigai breed emerged. The "plain" ecotype has massive body with higher yield of wool and meat; another one is "mountain" ecotype having less body mass. The first ecotype is more popular among the herders and livestock raisers.

Figure 1: Țisigai breed of sheep

Before 1950, the Țisigai breed grew in compact herds, in a smaller area, in the South-Eastern Plain and in the Dobrogean Plateau. Around 1950, the "țigaizare" (crossing the Țurcană breed with the Țisigai breed) took place on a large scale in the Bărăgan Plain, in the hilly and plateau areas in the south of the country, inside the Carpathian arch, in Transylvanian and the south and center of Moldova. At the beginning of this century, on the slopes of the Bucegi Mountains, in the localities of Teșila and Trestienii de Sus (Prahova area), and in the submontane areas of Covasna, Harghita and Mureș counties, Țisigai de șes breed was adapted, and crossbreed of the Țurcană breed (Figure 2) was adopted along with the mountain ecotype of the Țisigai breed.

Currently, the Țisigai breed represents about 26% of the total numbers of sheep in Romania, and is raised in the hilly, plateau, depression areas, and, to a lesser extent, in some sub-mountain areas. The Țurcană breed also comes from *Ovis vignei arkal*, having phylogenetic evolution and obvious phenotypic similarities, production, resistance and behavior resembling some breeds and other rustic breeds from Bulgaria, Greece, Yugoslavia, Italy, former URSS. It is the oldest breed in Romania, and its evolution dates back to ancient times.

Figure 2: Turcană sheep

Figure 3: Rotca sheep

The Turcana (Figure 2) continues to be the breed that holds the highest proportion (40%) of the total population. 3-4 decades ago, it represented over 60% of the population, growing both in the lowland and hill and mountain areas by virtue of its exceptional resistance and adaptability to different natural environmental conditions. This was maintained until 1950-1955 when the transformation of sheep was undertaken from thick wool sheep into semi-fine and fine wool producing sheep. It was accomplished by crossing Turcana with Țisigai in the hilly areas, and with Merinos in the plain areas. At present, it is widespread in the sub-mountainous and mountainous areas of the country, but sporadic herds continue to be increased in the hilly areas as well. Within this Turcana breed, 4 phenotypic variances are distinguished: white, black, grey and rotca. The white variety is the most frequent and widespread. It is especially appreciated for white wool from which clothes, Persian carpet and other folk-art products are made. This variety is the best milk producer breed. The black variety is raised in small numbers, especially in central and northern Romania where the sheep are crossed with Karakul rams to obtain skins. The grey variety is widespread in the hilly and sub-mountainous areas of northern Moldova, adjoining the localities of Bacău, Botoșani, Suceava and Piatra-Neamț. Both wool and "embers" are Brumaire. Due to their distinct morphoproductive characteristics and reproductive isolation, the Brumaire variety can be considered an independent breed. The improvement of this variety is to obtain valuable skins and to increase the milk production. The rotca variety (Figure 3) differs from the other varieties, especially by its "cap" horns twisted in the shape of a corkscrew, which is why it is having a different phylogenetic evolution.

4. Methodology

This research was performed on Țisigai and Turcana breeds of sheep. The total number of animals was 413 heads (Table 2). The age of the sheep studied was between 5 months and 6 years. The samples were analyzed for herd, milk production, wool production, meat production, the production of skins, furs and hides, the shelters and veterinary sanitary requirements during sheep breeding.

In the table 2, data of Țisigai and Țurcană sheep breeds is presented. In the two breeds, a very small percentage of sheep is registered having problems. Out of total 413 sheep, 202 (49%) sheep were milking, while 100 (24%) were barren sheep. 20 sheep had problems with calving. The feeding of sheep consists of grazing during the summer at low altitude and alpine pasture, and the fodder is produced within the farm during the winter.

Table 2: The sample of the sheep Țisigai and Țurcană studied

<i>Breeds</i>	<i>Total No. of Animals</i>	<i>Sheep producing milk</i>	<i>Barren sheep</i>	<i>Sheep having problems</i>	<i>Rams</i>	<i>Other sheep</i>
Turcana	228	100	60	15	10	43
Țisigai	185	102	40	5	6	32
Total	413	202	100	20	16	75

5. Result and Discussion

5.1 Milk Production

Since the Țurcană breed among all local breeds produces more milk, the milk production, on an average, is 80-110 liters per lactation (Lavinia, 2018); whereas improved variety of this breed produces 140-160 liters. The protein content is between 5.70% and 5.83% (Table 3). The fat content of milk progressively increases as the

lactation progresses. Similarly, the protein content also increases (Şonea, Maria, and Ionela, 2020), but has lower values.

Table 3: Monthly dynamics of the average protein content (n = sample size)

Year	n	Average % of protein per lactation	Average percentage of protein per lactation per month						
			Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6	Month 7
2015	45	5.83	5.69	5.86	5.10	5.86	6.13	6.38	-
2016	52	5.70	5.59	5.63	5.07	5.68	6.03	6.21	-
2017	50	5.77	5.62	5.73	5.11	5.79	5.98	6.42	-
2018	45	5.79	5.59	5.69	5.09	5.83	5.86	6.04	6.48
2019	25	5.86	5.68	5.72	5.13	5.69	6.11	6.19	6.56

In terms of fat content or protein content, the sheep reared at lower altitude are no significantly different from those raised in high-altitude (alpine) pastures. In both the cases, the protein content marked a slight decrease in the third month, which corresponds to the largest amount of milk (Lavinia, 2018). It shows that sheep raised in low altitude meadows are better than those raised in alpine pastures for the purpose of hay production (Lavinia, 2017). The use of low altitude meadows for hay production is more rational than their use as pasture.

5.2 Wool Production

The structure of the sheep hairs is important for wool production. The fibrillar composition and shape of the strands are determined by the characteristics of the follicular group. The hair follicles exist in two layers: one deeper layer correspond to the primary follicles, which generate long and thick fibers; and another superficial layer corresponds to the secondary follicles that generate short and thin fibers responsible for determining structurally the conical shape of the strand. In general, the wool produced from the hairs of Țurcană sheep is rough. When washed, it loses 30%-35% of weight (Figure 4). The washing efficiency varies between 65% and 70% in the sheep raised in mountainous conditions. The amount of wool varies depending on the feeding conditions and the growing area.

Wool production, calculated at STAS yield of 53% (Table 4), resulted on an average amount of wool per animal is given in table 4 having values of standard deviation and coefficient of variability.

Table 4: Data of wool production by Turcana breed

Year	Rams				Adult sheep			
	n	$x \pm sx$	s	cv	n	$x \pm sx$	s	cv
2015	17	3.87 ± 0.08	0.34	8.78	345	2.75 ± 0.75	0.75	27.24
2016	20	3.27 ± 0.08	0.39	11.91	395	2.33 ± 0.02	0.33	14.23
2017	23	3.18 ± 0.07	0.38	11.92	341	2.25 ± 0.01	0.28	12.47
2018	18	3.63 ± 0.11	0.46	12.66	348	2.43 ± 0.30	0.56	23.25
2019	21	3.88 ± 0.07	0.36	9.27	334	2.54 ± 0.01	0.31	12.20

n = sample size

$x \pm sx$ = average wool production per animal in kg

s = standard deviation

cv = coefficient of variability in %

Figure 4: Washed wool obtained from the Turcana breed

The wool washing efficiency (Figure 4) is influenced by hereditary characters and environmental factors. The percentage of impurities in the wool is closely related to the care and maintenance of sheep during herding, grazing and shelter care. The variation in the wool production (Table 4) is the outcome of some feeding errors. The most important physical and technological properties of wool include the length of the strands, the fineness of the fibers, their strength and extensibility. In general, the characteristics of wool differ from one ecotype of sheep breed to the another, and show a great variability in the coat, from individual to individual, both in terms of diameter and length (Figure 3). Such variation is also observed in the type of strand, pigmentation and degree of corrugation of the wool fibers. According to the absolute length of wool fibers, we have three types of fibers: long – over 16 cm; medium (9-15 cm) and short 8 cm. Short fibers have a weight of 30%, medium fibers 46.25%, and long fibers 23%. The absolute average length is determined on fiber sections and is illustrated in table 5.

Table 5: The relative and absolute length (cm) of the wool fibers

Relative length (cm)	Absolute length (cm)		
	<i>n</i>	$x \pm sx$	<i>cv</i> (%)
24.0	195	12.32 ± 0.48	51.29
27.0	136	16.08 ± 0.34	43.32
20.0	149	11.73 ± 1.30	31.62
23.0	181	13.85 ± 0.31	29.38
17.0	124	9.07 ± 0.39	48.40
20.0	138	9.54 ± 0.51	59.64
18.0	117	9.52 ± 0.36	41.70
24.0	118	12.60 ± 0.56	48.80
16.0	120	9.95 ± 0.33	36.18
21.0	132	12.66 ± 0.45	39.09

n = sample size

$x \pm sx$ = average wool production per animal in kg

cv = coefficient of variability in %

The data in the table 6 summarizes that the average diameter the fibers in the middle section is 72.42 microns in the long ones, 41.22 microns in the medium sized and 37.13 microns in the short ones. The variability in the diameter of long fibers, which increases from base to tip, is explained by different feeding conditions during the year and the physiological condition of the sheep. The larger diameter is obtained in May-September period when the sheep are grazed and weaned feeding the lambs.

The average diameter is presented in the table 6. On an average, the diameter per 1500 fibres is 50.29 microns with a coefficient of variability of 30.2%. This data exhibit that the shape and structure of the strand and the degree of corrugation have correlation with the absolute average length, the average diameter, the types of fiber in the strand, and the level of wool production. The wool characteristics depend on different biotypes of the Țurcană breed. It indicates that the future research must focus on selecting the most productive biotypes for increasing and improving the wool production. Absolute tear strength and extensibility are important properties of fiber, as they determine the strength and plasticity of wool fabrics. These properties are closely correlated with the fineness of the fiber, in the sense that the fine fibers have a lower strength and extensibility than the thick ones, thus having a correlation with the body region and environmental factors.

Table 6: The average diameter of the types of fibers in the strand of Țurcană sheep

Specification	Type of fiber	Fiber section location	Number of fibers	Diameter (in micron)	
				$x \pm sx$	cv
Sample of 10 sheep	Long	middle	500	72.42 ± 0.64	19.4
	Medium sized	middle	500	41.22 ± 0.58	31.3
	Short	middle	500	37.13 ± 0.49	29.3
Median	-	-	1500	50.26 ± 0.52	30.2

5.3. Meat Production

The research undertaken in recent years highlights that the Țurcană and Țisigai breeds are utilized for meat production of superior qualities. The rational use of improved adult sheep for meat production should be given due importance (Gavojdian *et al.*, 2012). 20-30% increase in meat quality was recorded if sheep was reconditioned, thus contributing to raising the economic efficiency of the meat production units based on large flocks of sheep (Figure 6).

In Romania, out of the 8 million sheep destined for meat production, annually 3 million heads represent the adult, reformed sheep, out of which over 1 million are of the Țurcană breed. Therefore, the rational use of reformed adult sheep for meat production is an action that should be given due importance. Only by reconditioning the reformed sheep can increase the meat by 20-30% with improvement of its quality, thus contributing to raising the economic efficiency of the units with large flocks of sheep (Figure 7).

5.4 Production of Hides, Skins and Furs

The Țurcană breed produces high-quality leathers. The skin from Țurcană is more resistant because the collagen fibers are woven together in a denser structure. The skin is also more resistant to elongation and tearing. This resistance of the skin is the result of the lower number of hair follicles per unit area. The thickness of the skin is in two layers: the primary follicles are deeper, and the secondary follicles are closer to the surface of the skin (Figure 6). The quality of the skins is determined by the conditioning by a series of natural and genetic factors e.g., individuality, sex, health, skin size during

pruning, physiological condition of the animal, slaughtering season, age, feeding conditions, care and shelter.

Țurcană lambs are slaughtered for fur before the wool exceeds 3-5 cm length. Fur is produced under strict compliance of the sanitary-veterinary measures.

Calendar of sanitary-veterinary actions

Sheep utilization systems guide to take measures to prevent and combat different diseases.

In sheep, morbidity and losses are the consequence of diseases caused by non-sanitary conditions. Such diseases are chiefly parasitic diseases, especially those come from pasture (Figure 9). Therefore, to ensure better health of animals, strict supervision of sheep applying clinical observations, anatomical-pathological examinations, feed control, hygiene maintenance, etc. is necessary.

Figure 5: Sheep carcass

The sanitary-veterinary actions undertaken are grouped as follows:

Purpose:

Detection / Prevention / Tackling

Specifics:

Mandatory / Optional / Of necessity

Season:

Stable / Pasture

Growth and exploitation:
Extensive / Intensive

Figure 6: Sheep semi-casing Turcană

Figure 7: Sheep skin coat

Figure 8: Prime wool, shearing sheep

Figure 9: Sheep fold

Figure 10: Traditional shelter for sheep

Regarding the sanitary-veterinary actions in the extensive exploitation system, they are grouped as follows:

- a) In the winter season, under stable conditions, the following is performed:
 1. general and permanent control of feeding in order to prevent abortions, infections such as hysteresis, hypogalaxy and lung diseases in lambs;
 2. immuno-prophylactic actions, which consist of the serological examination for the detection of epididymitis and tuberculosis separately; vaccinations against anaerobiosis, salmonellar abortion and agalaxia;
 3. antiparasitic actions, which consist of the detection of scabies, the isolation and treatment of animals with local lesions, and treatment against fasciolosis, estrosis.
- b) In the spring season, once the grazing is done, the following is performed:
 1. vaccination against anthrax and enterotoxemia in lambs;
 2. organization of prophylactic grazing;
 3. antiparasitic actions, such as pasture control and ameliorating and chemical interventions on them.

Regarding the sanitary-veterinary actions in the intensive fattening system, they are grouped as follows:

- A) For young:
 1. Organization of the in-patient and the sanitary-veterinary provider (Figure10);
 2. Loss according to possible clinical signs, especially hypotreptic ones; prophylactic treatments against pulmonary diseases and against pulmonary and gastric strongylatoses;
 3. Surveillance of feed to avoid indigestion, biochemical indigestion, uro-lithiasis, listeriosis;
 4. Treatments against scabies, monilioze, dictiocaulosis;
 5. Vaccinations.
- B) For adult sheep:
 1. Treatment against scabies, fasciolosis and dictyocaulosis, pododermatitis;
 2. Vaccinations against anaerobes, foot-and-mouth disease and anthrax.

The lambs are vaccinated with Evomec and the yolk treatment. The bathing is also done with Lindaved once a year in spring. Pruning is done twice a year in spring and autumn.

6. Conclusion

Sheep breeding is a traditional activity. The diversity of the products they produce, the low energy and fodder consumption make the breeding and utilization of sheep a sustainable and profitable activity. Raising traditional sheep breeds (e.g., Tisigai and Turcana) in the mountain areas has sustained for centuries. The local people consider Tisigai and Turcana sheep breeds perfectly adapting to geo-climatic and transhumance conditions, providing them with daily necessities, and producing the products for market. There are areas in Romania having preserved valuable specimens of sheep, the traditions and customs related to the breeding and harnessing these sheep. These specimens, which represent the genetic stock of the traditional breeds, can be used in the larger breeding program of sheep in the mountainous areas of Romania.

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The ARRIVE Essential 10

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Item	Recommendation	Section/line number, or reason for not reporting
Study design 1	For each experiment, provide brief details of study design including: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The groups being compared, including control groups. If no control group has been used, the rationale should be stated. The experimental unit (e.g. a single animal, litter, or cage of animals). 	Total number of 413 animals studied, the following criteria were established: altitude, shearing and reconditioning. A lot of animals
Sample size 2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Specify the exact number of experimental units allocated to each group, and the total number in each experiment. Also indicate the total number of animals used. Explain how the sample size was decided. Provide details of any <i>a priori</i> sample size calculation, if done. 	Percentage of milk protein: total number of animals 217; wool production: fibre number 1500, sample 10 sheep; meat production: no fattened animals 23, duration 50 days. randomly
Inclusion and exclusion criteria 3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Describe any criteria used for including and excluding animals (or experimental units) during the experiment, and data points during the analysis. Specify if these criteria were established <i>a priori</i>. If no criteria were set, state this explicitly. For each experimental group, report any animals, experimental units or data points not included in the analysis and explain why. If there were no exclusions, state so. For each analysis, report the exact value of <i>n</i> in each experimental group. 	Milk production: criterion: sheep that have calved at least once. Total number of animals: 217. Maintained at low altitude 50 sheep, high altitude 50 sheep. The protein content increases slightly, regardless of the altitude. There were no exclusions Wool - in 2015 no animals 17; 2016 no animals 20; 2017 no animals 23; 2018 no animals 18; 2019 No. of animals 21 Wool fibers 1600, Milk - in 2015 there would be 45
Randomisation 4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> State whether randomisation was used to allocate experimental units to control and treatment groups. If done, provide the method used to generate the randomisation sequence. Describe the strategy used to minimise potential confounders such as the order of treatments and measurements, or animal/cage location. If confounders were not controlled, state this explicitly. 	It's not necessary animals raised at high and low altitudes
Blinding 5	Describe who was aware of the group allocation at the different stages of the experiment (during the allocation, the conduct of the experiment, the outcome assessment, and the data analysis).	The sheep breeder.
Outcome measures 6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Clearly define all outcome measures assessed (e.g. cell death, molecular markers, or behavioural changes). For hypothesis-testing studies, specify the primary outcome measure, i.e. the outcome measure that was used to determine the sample size. 	No changes were identified. Maintained at low altitude 50 sheep, high altitude 50 sheep
Statistical methods 7	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Provide details of the statistical methods used for each analysis, including software used. Describe any methods used to assess whether the data met the assumptions of the statistical approach, and what was done if the assumptions were not met. 	No software was used. Calculate: average and coefficient of variability. The data were close to those described by other researchers
Experimental animals 8	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Provide species-appropriate details of the animals used, including species, strain and substrain, sex, age or developmental stage, and, if relevant, weight. Provide further relevant information on the provenance of animals, health/immune status, genetic modification status, genotype, and any previous procedures. 	Race characteristics described in the paper Race characteristics described in the paper
Experimental procedures 9	For each experimental group, including controls, describe the procedures in enough detail to allow others to replicate them, including: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> What was done, how it was done and what was used. When and how often. Where (including detail of any acclimatisation periods). Why (provide rationale for procedures). 	farm animals and existing farm data were used. Data were calculated The research was conducted three times a year. Mountain and submontane area biannual shearing of sheep is beneficial for wool production and weaning efficiency, now it is not practiced. Reconditioning of animals before slaughter increases the slaughter
Results 10	For each experiment conducted, including independent replications, report: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Summary/descriptive statistics for each experimental group, with a measure of variability where applicable (e.g. mean and SD, or median and range). If applicable, the effect size with a confidence interval. 	farm animals and existing farm data were used. It's not necessary. No changes were identified

Author' Declarations and Essential Ethical Compliances

Authors' Contributions (in accordance with ICMJE criteria for authorship)

Contribution	Author 1	Author 2	Author 3	Author 4
Conceived and designed the research or analysis	Yes	Yes	No	No
Collected the data	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Contributed to data analysis & interpretation	Yes	No	No	No
Wrote the article/paper	Yes	No	No	No
Critical revision of the article/paper	Yes	No	No	No
Editing of the article/paper	Yes	No	No	No
Supervision	Yes	No	No	No
Project Administration	Yes	No	No	No
Funding Acquisition	Yes	No	No	No
Overall Contribution Proportion (%)	60	20	10	10

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Research involving human bodies (Helsinki Declaration)

Has this research used human subjects for experimentation? No

Research involving animals (ARRIVE Checklist)

Has this research involved animal subjects for experimentation? Yes

Research involving Plants

During the research, the authors followed the principles of the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Convention on the Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora. Yes

Research on Indigenous Peoples and/or Traditional Knowledge

Has this research involved Indigenous Peoples as participants or respondents? No

(Optional) PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses)

Have authors complied with PRISMA standards? No

Competing Interests/Conflict of Interest

Authors have no competing financial, professional, or personal interests from other parties or in publishing this manuscript. No

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